

Verification of the System Code ARCADIA and Loading Pattern Optimization using FARGO for a Small Modular Reactor

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ABSTRACT

This work is divided in two main topics: the first attempts of Validation and Verification (V&V, in this paper only verification is done) of the system code ARCADIA for simulating a Small Modular Reactor (SMR) and the application of the code FARGO to the same SMR for Loading Pattern Optimization.

The SMR simulated is the NuSCALE-like model presented on the European Project McSAFER. The mentioned SMR is a Small Pressurized Water Reactor.

The two-step approach (lattice code/nodal simulation) is applied for the analysis, generating the cross sections with the lattice code APOLLO2-A, and applying ARTEMIS with thermal-hydraulic feedback from COBRA-FLX for the 3D core simulations.

The results obtained with APOLLO2-A are compared against results obtained with the Monte Carlo Simulation code Serpent. The Serpent model is developed at Framatome as well.

The results of the nodal simulation obtained with ARTEMIS are compared against results published by other participants of the European Project McSAFER.

FARGO is used, in the second part of this work, for optimizing the existing loading pattern, trying to achieve a longer cycle while respecting the safety parameters e.g., Moderator Temperature Coefficient (MTC).

Keywords: ARCADIA, FARGO, SMR, V&V, Loading Pattern Optimization

1. INTRODUCTION

Framatome's nuclear core design and safety analysis code system ARCADIA [1] [2] [3] has been extensively verified and validated with a rich database over the years. Still, the ARCADIA team finds it important to further enhance the already rich validation and verification database by participating in different international projects and benchmarks [4]. Mainly, it is important for Framatome to increase the validation and verification to other types of reactors, taking in account their possible relevance for the future of the energy production [5]. It is important for Framatome as well to show and enhance the capabilities of the tools developed by the company for Loading Pattern Optimization (LPO). FARGO which is a set of software tools for integrated lattice and LPO has been recently successfully applied for several projects [6]. Based on this success, the question was raised how FARGO could support the optimization of other types of cores such as SMR.

To achieve these goals and answer the questions raised, Framatome decided to participate in the European Project McSAFER [7]. This European Project aims to contribute to neutronic and thermal-hydraulic safety analysis for diverse types of Small Modular Reactors (SMR). The data available within the project for the different reactors is a combination of public real data and engineering assumptions.

The data available include the following reactor types (the word "like" is added as a suffix to denote the combination of real data and assumptions):

- NuSCALE-like
- CAREM-like
- SMART-like
- F-SMR

It was decided at Framatome to start the process of Validation and Verification (V&V) of ARCADIA for SMR by simulating the NuSCALE-like core, since it is an integrated Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) and to optimize the original NuSCALE-like LPO with FARGO. Code-to-code comparison is presented in this paper, since no measured data is available. However, this is just the first step, and it is planned to continue the V&V for diverse types of SMR.

2. THE ARCADIA CODE SYSTEM

ARCADIA is an advanced 3D code system developed by Framatome [8]. ARCADIA offers a 3D state-of-the-art neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, thermal-mechanics simulation solution for steady-state and transient simulations. It allows for nodal and pin-by-pin calculations. ARCADIA uses the following codes as main modules:

- APOLLO2-A (lattice physics calculations) [9]. It is based on the APOLLO2 kernel developed by CEA (Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives) and adapted by Framatome for industrial applications. It solves the Boltzmann transport equation in a multi-group scheme and for generic unstructured geometries. It can be applied for the simulation of Pressurized and Boiling Water Reactors (PWR and BWR).
- ARTEMIS (3D core simulator) [10]. It is a modular code which includes different analysis capabilities e.g., high-performance multi-group diffusion and transport flux solvers. Each physical model is coded into a class and implemented as a FORTRAN95 module. The modules are coupled with a coarse grain parallelization using MPI (message passing interface) and fine grain parallelization using OpenMP. The main modules of ARTEMIS are:
 - Neutron Flux Solver (steady-state and transient): uses multi-group nodal diffusion approaches with a multi-level rebalancing methodology applied as non-linear acceleration approach.
 - Thermal-hydraulics: the sub-channel code COBRA-FLX is coupled as the thermal-hydraulics module [11]. It allows 3D steady-state and transient full-core as well as sub-channel analysis.
 - Fuel Rod Module (FRM). Resolves the non-linear heat transfer equation in representative fuel rods to evaluate the Doppler feedback in fuel pins [8].

ARTEMIS is coupled externally with a core monitoring system (ARGOS), two system thermal-hydraulics codes (CATHARE 2 and S-RELAP5) and a fuel rod performance code (GALILEO). All components are embedded in a user-friendly environment named LADON.

3. FARGO-LPO

FARGO is a set of Framatome's software optimization tools. It includes two optimization methods, lattice and loading pattern optimization (LPO) [6]. For this work only the LPO is relevant and described.

In the LPO method, the ARTEMIS code is used for the physics calculations of the core. Several algorithms have been or are being implemented into the system based on the MIDAS system from NCSU [12], including:

- Parallel simulated annealing (PSA)
- Genetic algorithm (GA)
- Reinforcement learning (RL)

The parameters, which can be optimized are the maximum boron concentration over the cycle, pin power peaking factor (FQ), enthalpy rise hot channel factor (FDH), radial peaking factor (Fxy), cycle length, maximum fuel rod burnup, average fuel assembly discharge burnup, MTC, etc.

4. DESCRIPTION OF THE NUSCALE-LIKE CORE

The NuSCALE SMR is an integrated PWR designed by NuSCALE, being the first SMR to be certified for use in the USA. On one of the first stages of the design, the reactor thermal power was 160 MWth. Currently the design being certified is for 250 MWth. However, the data presented in the European Project McSAFER is based on the 160 MWth design, completing the missing proprietary data by those generated on base of experience and engineering judgement [13]. Framatome GmbH is a member of the user group of McSAFER and hence has access to the data.

The core consists of thirty-seven fuel assemblies with six different enrichments from 1.50 to 4.55 w/o ^{235}U , one of those containing sixteen fuel rods with containing 8% Gd_2O_3 . The fuel assemblies have a configuration of 17x17 fuel rods with twenty-four guide tubes and an instrumentation tube (see *Figure 1*)

Figure 1. NuSCALE-like core loading pattern (left) and example of a fuel assembly layout, in this case with 16 fuel rods containing Gd_2O_3 (right).

The specifications describe the core with a theoretical radial heavy reflector defined by a mixing of stainless steel and water. Four control rod banks are described as well (two regulating and two shutdown banks). For further details of the geometry see [13].

5. CALCULATIONS - OPERATIONAL CONDITIONS AND METHODOLOGY

This work is divided between two main steps, the ARCADIA V&V, and the FARGO optimization. The ARCADIA V&V itself is divided in different steps, which are detailed below. In two of the steps, ARCADIA calculations are compared against an equivalent model generated with a Monte Carlo code, in this case Serpent [14] (version 2.2.1, with the library JEFF3.1.1 [15]). It was decided to use Serpent for the comparison, since there is user experience available in Framatome GmbH and Serpent is a Monte

Carlo code developed and dedicated for nuclear reactor simulations. Serpent is used as well by other participants of the European project McSAFER, but for the purpose of this work, it was decided to develop our own model inside Framatome, to avoid differences due to the variation of the models. The steps for the ARCADIA calculations are:

- Code-to-code comparison of the fuel assembly simulations done with APOLLO2-A and Serpent. The fuel cross sections are generated by APOLLO2-A with a symmetry of 1/8 of the fuel assembly and using the library JEFF3.1.1 [15]. The reflector cross sections are done in 2D using the Equivalent Reflector Model (ERM) [16].
- Code-to-code comparison of the steady-state BOC core simulations done with ARTEMIS and Serpent. The operation conditions used for these calculations are detailed in *Table I*.
- Depletion calculation with ARTEMIS (for the comparison against the optimized loading pattern generated with FARGO). The depletion is done with all rods out (ARO) and until the natural end of cycle (EOC-N).

The results of both code-to-code comparisons were done in the frame of the master thesis done in Framatome by the student B. P. Karakaş [5].

Table I. Operating conditions BOC NuSCALE-like core.

Parameter	Value
Core power	160 MWth
System pressure	12.76 MPa
Core flow rate	587.15 kg/s (7.3 % in bypass)
Core inlet temperature	531.45 K

Once the ARCADIA calculations were performed, it was proceeded to the optimization with FARGO. The optimization criteria were:

- Boron
- FDH
- Cycle length
- Moderator temperature coefficient

The optimization was done using the PSA methodology and applying the optimization to a symmetry of 1/8 of the core.

6. RESULTS

6.1. ARCADIA-Serpent comparison

Table II shows the results of the lattice calculations performed by APOLLO2-A and their comparison with Serpent. The maximal pin power for the 6 types of fuel assemblies as well as the k_{∞} are presented. The differences in k_{∞} are below 75 pcm and the pin power are below 0.7% in all the cases.

Table II. Results of k_{∞} and pin power calculations and their comparison using APOLLO2-A and Serpent.

Assembly	k_{∞}			Max. Pin power		
	APOLLO2-A	Serpent	Δk_{∞} [pcm]	APOLLO2-A	Serpent	Absolute difference [%]
A01	0.98727	0.98672	55	1.031	1.037	-0.58
A02	1.00972	1.00910	62	1.033	1.038	-0.48
B01	1.15435	1.15426	9	1.042	1.048	-0.57
B02	1.16603	1.16597	6	1.043	1.049	-0.57
C01	1.28492	1.28509	-17	1.053	1.060	-0.66
C02	1.15026	1.15100	-74	1.140	1.142	-0.18

In Figure 2 the comparison between the power distributions obtained by the core simulations done with ARTEMIS and Serpent are shown. In both cases (radial and axial) the differences are below 3.0%. The in-out tendency in the power radial differences, as well as the increment towards the core axial periphery could be due to the simplified reflector data found in [13]. The improvement on the reflector models could lead to a better code-to-code agreement. However, given the circumstances, these results are considered acceptable.

Figure 2. Radial power distribution differences $[(ARTEMIS - Serpent)/Serpent*100]$ (top) and axial power distributions and differences $[(ARTEMIS - Serpent)/Serpent*100]$ (bottom).

6.2. Loading Pattern Optimization with FARGO

Starting from the configuration of *Figure 1*, the LP was optimized. The fuel assembly with 2.60 w/o ^{235}U enrichment was omitted by FARGO and the loading pattern was re-arranged to increase the cycle length while maintaining the safety margins. The cycle length obtained with the original pattern was of 659 EFPD and the MTC was -0.403 pcm/K.

One of the most difficult safety margins to maintain in SMR is the MTC, which is the ratio of the variation of reactivity with respect on the moderator's temperature variations and needs to be negative. The difficulty to maintain this parameter negative in SMR is due to different factors, e.g.:

- Lower moderator to fuel ratio
- Higher leakage effects
- Higher enrichment and/or the use of burnable absorbers

All these factors weaken or reverse the reactivity feedback that normally makes MTC negative in large light-water reactors.

With the optimized loading pattern, the achieved cycle length is 1086 EFPD (an increment of 12 months) and the MTC was improved to a value of -5.629 pcm/K.

The ratio of the total mass of ^{235}U with respect of the cycle length is taken as a parameter to see if the new loading pattern improved the use of ^{235}U . The ratio of the original loading pattern is 0.391 $\text{kg}^{235}\text{U}/\text{EFPD}$, while the ratio of the optimized loading pattern is 0.304 $\text{kg}^{235}\text{U}/\text{EFPD}$. This shows a better use of the fuel.

In *Figure 3* the boron concentration, axial power offset, FQ and FDH throughout the cycle for both, original and optimized loading patterns, are shown.

Figure 3. Results of the depletion calculation obtained by ARTEMIS for the original and optimized loading patterns. Top left boron concentration, right axial offset; bottom left FQ, right FDH.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The ARCADIA simulations (lattice with APOLLO2-A and core 3D with ARTEMIS) for the NuSCALE-like core steady-state cases show good agreement with the results generated by using the Monte Carlo code Serpent. ARCADIA is capable as well to simulate depletion calculations of SMR of the kind of the NuSCALE-like model.

FARGO has achieved to optimize the NuSCALE-like loading pattern by increasing the first cycle length by 12 months while maintaining the safety margins. Given the SMR diversity in terms of core design and core size, it is foreseen to apply ARCADIA and FARGO to other types of PWR-like SMRs. This will allow core loading pattern optimization based on advanced licensed 3-D code system and complement this technical analysis with economical consideration on fuel cycle cost impact to propose core loading patterns that are optimized both technically and economically.

It is foreseen to apply ARCADIA and FARGO for other types of SMR.

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